

Khizer Hayat Judgment: Whether An Escape From The Responsibility To Sift Grain From The Chaff?

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 30, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 31, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Rule, Judicial Proceedings, Witness, Mistake, Proof.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6400010</p>	<p><i>The article examines critically the Khizer Hayat judgment of the Supreme Court of Pakistan whereby the falsus rule was made applicable to judicial proceedings across Pakistan. It will trace the history of the rule in common law jurisdiction, particularly those of Britain and India. Moreover, it will suggest that the judgment goes to great lengths to discuss the application of falsus in murder cases where a witness willfully implicates innocent along with guilty to seek revenge, however, it leaves no margin for mistake or memory lapse as an explanation for incorrect testimony. Additionally, it will assert that the reliance of the Supreme Court on Islamic injunctions to justify falsus rule is misplaced because the quoted Hadith and Quranic injunctions only condemn the false testimony, nowhere do they require disbelieving a witness who tells a lie in one part of his statement. In the end, the article will conclude that the issue of false testimony was well taken care of under Pakistan's jurisprudence before Khizer Hayat. As proof, Justice Munir in his famous judgment Crown v. Ghulam Muhammad (1951) set forth the rule, if a witness is caught in a lie about a materiel part, his rest of the statement may be disbelieved unless strongly corroborated by circumstances or other available evidence. It will be suggested that Ghulam Muhammad's doctrine should be revived, otherwise, the impression may take roots that the courts are shying away from their responsibility to sift grain from chaff.</i></p>

Introduction

The maxim *falsus in uno falsus in omnibus* refers to an ancient rule of evidence implying that if a witness is caught in a lie in one part of his statement under oath, his entire testimony should be disbelieved. This rule was made in-applicable to criminal proceedings in Pakistan through case law. The Judges in their wisdom observed that the witnesses of sub-continent were naturally inclined towards exaggeration and economizing with truth, so margin would have to be given to half-truths. In other words, it would be unrealistic to expect that such witnesses would be forthcoming who would tell nothing but truth. Therefore, if falsus rule was enforced, prosecution of offender would become virtually impossible. The principle came under discussion in a landmark judgment authored by a two-member bench of the Supreme Court in 2019 entitled 'Notice to Khizer Hayat.' In this case, a murder accused was acquitted on the basis that one of the PWs Khizer Hayat while giving testimony was caught in a lie. It so happened that a DW produced evidence that the said PW was a police constable and could not have been present at the scene of crime because the crime took place at Lahore whereas the said PW was posted in Narowal at the relevant time. The story of the prosecution was discredited further when the complainant stated that he saw the occurrence as he came out of his house to see off PW Khizer Hayat. The Supreme Court in Khizer Hayat discussed at length the evolution of the falsus rule. It went on to observe that in the early 20th century although the rule was abandoned in England, it continued to apply in the US and some other jurisdictions. It referred to a number of pre-partition judgments to establish that Indian witnesses were inherently unreliably as they used to twist the facts in their testimony. Likewise, the Supreme Court also analyzed the culture of India where true cases had to be placed on false foundations and advanced through false testimony. Furthermore, it blamed the judges and lawyers of Mofussil (lower courts) to have aggravated the situation by giving consideration to the number of witnesses and quantity of evidence in preference over its quality. Lastly, the Supreme Court held that it was quite logical to disbelieve a witness, a part of whose testimony was found to be false. Such witness cannot be believed at all, in regard to rest of his statement.

This article will suggest that although the judgment has painstakingly thrashed the history of the rule to justify its application, it fails to address the most obvious pitfall that the witnesses do not always exaggerate or economize with truth because they intentionally want to lie. Instead, they can be incorrect because of memory loss, inattentiveness and shock of the incident. To illustrate, QSO 1984 contains provisions on refreshing of memory enabling the witness to look at his statement under section 161 CRPC. By the same token, modern psychiatrists argue that human memory tends to be selective and we often remember the things appealing to our

materialistic self-interest. So, the article will point out that if a witness lies about one aspect of the case, it is not necessary that he will be lying about the whole occurrence. As pointed out by Medina, our minds cannot multi-task and are programmed to focus on one thing at a time. Thus, to explain holes in our story caused by memory lapse, we invent facts. The article will maintain that previous approach taken by the Supreme Court in *Ghulam Muhammad v. Crown 1951* was quite practical as compared to the one adopted in *Khizer Hayat* which sets forth unrealistic standards for accepting testimony. The article will show that the judgment in *Ghulam Muhammad* was based on the time tested principle of sifting grain from the chaff requiring the judges to find out the truth, while *Khizer Hayat* principle absolves the judges from all responsibility by allowing them to discard the testimony a part of which is found to be false. It will be demonstrated that the underlying assumption of *Khizer Hayat* is misconceived which set out that the role of a judge is only to see if the evidence on record connects the accused with the crime beyond reasonable doubt, by contrast digging out the truth is task of the investigating agencies. It will be urged that digging out the truth also becomes a function of the judges at the time of appraisal of evidence.

1. Two Major Challenges to Khizer Hayat judgments

1.1. Assumptions relating to human psychology

A number of psychiatrists have made observations based on scientific reasoning that many a times we humans cook up stories to make sense of what we have only half- seen or heard. Similarly, it has been argued that human memory can retain a fact for 20 seconds without additions or deletions, unless it is repeated. Furthermore, we tend to make assumptions and see a fact in the light of our personal experience or genetic biases. Hence, it is beyond the realm of possibility that a witness should narrate a fact as it is, without exaggerations or missing out on some details. Discarding his entire testimony on this basis alone can be dangerous for public trust in our fragile justice system. All in all, it can be propounded that exaggerations and economizing with truth may not necessarily be deliberate as presumed by the Supreme Court in *Khizer Hayat*.

1.2. Facts relied by court to doubt the truthfulness of Khizer Hayat

In the same way, the facts of *Khizer Hayat* case themselves beg answers to some critical questions. For example, how did the court come to a definitive conclusion that if *Khizer Hayat* was posted at Narowal, he could not have gone to visit his relatives at Lahore? His posting at Narowal only established a rebuttable presumption of his absence from the scene of crime; the court appears to have taken it as a conclusive proof. After all, it is common practice in Pakistan that government employees leave their stations for overnight visits to their friends and relatives without informing their departments. Therefore, it is possible that *Khizer Hayat* could be telling the truth when he said that he was present on the scene of crime. Forasmuch as the Supreme Court was bashing sub-continental witnesses for their inclination to tell lies, it should have also taken the trouble to discuss the casual and non-professional attitude of our government employees in general.

2. Evolution of falsus rule in Pakistan

In *Khizer Hayat*, the Supreme Court referred to a number of previous judgments to shed light on the country's jurisprudence on the falsus doctrine. Of these, special emphasis was laid on *Ghulam Muhammad v. the Crown*. In this case, five persons were killed and 14 accused were charged for their murder. Two of the accused somehow proved that they were in police lock up at the time of the occurrence, so they could not have been present at the scene of the crime. Because of this exculpatory evidence, the trial court disbelieved the witnesses against the other accused too. However, the High Court set aside the trial court's judgment by reason that if a witness is found to have lied about one material aspect of the case, it does not automatically follow that their entire testimony should be disbelieved about other aspects of the case. If there is strong circumstantial evidence, corroborating the witness testimony about other aspects, the same should be believed. In other words, the courts in Pakistan do not act upon the principle that the credibility of a witness is indivisible. It is possible that a witness may be lying about some aspects of an occurrence but the same witness may be telling the truth about other aspects.

Although our superior courts initially rejected the doctrine by observing that people of the sub-continent had a propensity to lie to trap their enemies, after *Ghulam Muhammad* they started to give it partial recognition. According to the Supreme Court, even dying declarations of the people of Punjab should be taken with a pinch of salt because in spite of the presumption of truth attached to it because of the prospect of impending death, the deceased may add the names of some innocents along with guilty to take revenge from his enemies. However, the statement of a witness, if found to be false about the involvement of one accused, should not be taken to mean that the same will be false about implication of the other accused, and should be believed as against others, if supported by circumstantial evidence.

In the light of the above rulings of the superior courts of Pakistan, it can be argued that in the jurisprudence of Pakistan prior to *Khizer Hayat*, the integrity of a witness was deemed to be divisible and it was the task of the court to sift grain from the chaff or to separate truth from falsehood. So, the courts back then held the view that lying about one material aspect of the case does not make the testimony unreliable in its entirety. This view was slightly changed in 1951 when the Lahore High Court held in *Ghulam Muhammad* that a person who commits

perjury in one material aspect of the case, his statement should be disbelieved unless corroborated by strong circumstantial evidence.

The Supreme Court noted in *Khizer Hayat* that the Privy Council diverted from the conclusion drawn in *Ghulam Muhammad*. According to it, if there are two accused, as against one the witness's statement is believed and against the other the same witness is disbelieved, in such a position, both accused should be re-tried. Earlier in this case, the appellate court had sustained the conviction of one accused whereas a re-trial was ordered as against the other because the witness was found to have committed perjury about a material aspect. The Privy Council thus ordered that the interest of the justice will be served if both are re-tried. Therefore, as per the views of the Supreme Court in *Khizer Hayat*, the law has been misconstrued in the past by superior courts of Pakistan because of extraneous and practical reasons rather than jurisprudential and legal reasons. For instance, Justice Munir rationalized his 1951 decision by way of the argument that the task of a judge is to get to the truth of the matter; he is required to sift grain from the chaff. Conversely, the Supreme Court held in *Khizer Hayat*, a judge's task is to see whether in the light of available evidence, the accused can be held guilty beyond reasonable doubt of the crime charged against him. The Supreme Court went on to observe that digging out the truth is the job of investigating agencies. I respectfully differ with this view, the agencies and the courts both are required to get to the truth. The police perform this task by collection of evidence, at the same time the courts do this by appreciating the evidence or considering its weight.

3. Shortcomings of Kizer Hayat

3.1. Fixation with one kind of perjury only

Throughout *Khizer Hayat*, the honorable members of the bench concerned themselves with one kind of perjury only, i.e. when the complainant deliberately implicates innocent accused along with the guilty. That said, it is not necessary that false implication is intentional every time; it can be caused by mistaken identity or pressure. Such an implication can result, for example in response to the loaded questions of an investigating officer or the witness having been unnerved by tormenting persuasions by the police. Should this false implication result in automatic acquittal of the other accused? Of course not, because judges are supposed to weigh the evidence keeping in view its corroboration by the circumstances. If the suggestible witness lies about the role of one accused under the pressure exerted by the investigating agency, it will be dangerous to disbelieve the entire prosecution story. Clearly, therefore, *Khizer Hayat* misses out on contemplating *falsus* in the backdrop of a situation where the witness/ complainant implicates the innocent accused upon the prompting of the investigating officer.

Likewise, the Supreme Court should have considered the application of *falsus* in situations where the complainant/ witness presumed logically that the innocent accused too must have been involved in the occurrence. A case in point is where the innocent accused has been threatening the victim with dire consequences; the witness may logically presume his guilt. Thus, it can be argued, if the application of *falsus* rule is important to prevent false implication of the innocent accused, its in- application is equally crucial to ensure that the guilty accused may not go scot free because of one mistaken identity formulated on logical deduction. Similarly, in a state of shock a witness cannot be expected to remember with exactitude names of his attackers.

In view of the above, the implication of innocent accused may be a result of mistaken identity caused by an unclear view, or logical assumption based on previous animosity between the victim and the accused. In suchlike cases, the principle laid down by CJ Munir in *Ghulam Muhammad* appears far more useful in the appraisal of evidence. It requires that in case a witness is proved to have committed perjury in one material aspect of the case, his remaining statement should not be accepted unless corroborated by the circumstances. This rule provides a middle ground and takes care of both situations i.e. false implication as well as the real culprits going off the hook due to one mistake by a witness or his intentional lie motivated by the duress or self-interest. However, now it stands overturned by *Khizer Hayat* according to which if a witness is caught in a lie in one aspect of the case, his entire testimony should be disbelieved. The rule is based on the premise that if a witness lies about the involvement of some of the accused in an occurrence, his false statement provides benefit of doubt to all other accused.

3.2. Islamic principle of indivisibility of testimony

In a judgment pre-dating *Khizer Hayat* it was observed that one of the basic principles of Islamic law is that if a witness commits perjury in respect of one of the accused, his testimony shall be disbelieved against all other accused. So, under the Islamic jurisprudence, the *falsus* rule does apply as the credibility of the witness is taken to be indivisible. Having established this, what needs to be discussed is how Islamic law will view a witness who mistakenly implicates an innocent accused in addition to guilty ones falling prey to mistaken identity error. *Khizer Hayat* case nowhere seems to question the assumption that one who lies does this on purpose. On the other hand, there are a number of provisions in QSO including those on refreshing memory and relevancy of facts, suggesting that human memory tends to fade with time and identity of an unknown accused ought to be established during investigation to contradict or corroborate the witness during trial. To lend credence to this, the psychologists are of the view that we humans often see what we want to see and our brains are not good at

multitasking, thus they store in the conscious memory what we have been actively focusing on. In the light of above, it can be suggested that the indivisibility of a witness' credibility hypothesis does not find support in modern scientific and neurological research. A witness can be right in regard to some aspects of the same occurrence and be mistaken or delirious in regard to the others. Islam being a complete code of life adapts to the needs of time. It will be hard to imagine that such a practical religion gives no consideration to concepts such as mistaken identity, delirium or duress, when determining credibility of a witness' testimony. Even with strict interpretation of indivisibility of testimony, Islamic law would more likely take the balanced approach of requiring corroboration for remaining testimony, instead of discarding it altogether. Despite the fact Wigmore calls it a useless rule which is not practicable considering the issues discussed above, the Supreme Court of Pakistan made it binding for the subordinate courts under article 189 of the constitution. Inasmuch as the Supreme Court cited some Quranic verses and Hadith to justify the application of the rule, it appears that the Court erred in the interpretation, as the said Islamic injunctions seemingly allude to perjury rather than the falsus rule. Nonetheless, by observing that the government cannot legislate on the matters settled by the Islamic law, the Supreme Court appears to have snatched the legislative power of the parliament by the cautioning the violation of Islamic injunctions.

3.3 The rule concerns with weight rather than admissibility of evidence

The Khizer Hayat judgment makes it obvious that the falsus principle has been discussed by the Supreme Court as a rule establishing admissibility of evidence. On the other hand, some scholars are of the view that this rule relates to the weight and appreciation of evidence. Consequently, it is for the court to decide whether a testimony should be taken into consideration for recording conviction or acquittal if it is proved to be false in one respect. Taking into account the distinction of weight and admissibility of evidence, CJ Munir's 1951 judgment in Ghulam Muhammad provides a better mechanism to appreciate the evidence. In case, the remaining testimony finds strong circumstantial support, it may be believed, otherwise, it should be discarded in its entirety.

3.4 The assumption that absence of falsus will encourage perjury

Khizer Hayat judgment goes on to suggest that perjury is a serious offence under chapter 11 of Pakistan Penal Code attracting serious punishment. Making falsus principle inapplicable in Pakistan will lead to encouraging perjury. In the words of the Supreme Court, courts cannot permit what is forbidden by law. If the witness and party calling is aware that one lie would destroy their whole case, they would refrain from giving false evidence. This argument has a serious flaw, under section 191 of PPC, perjury is defined as telling a lie when you are legally bound to speak the truth; it nowhere says if a witness is proved wrong in one part of his statement due to whatever reason, he or she should be regarded as a perjurer. Perjury can be said to have been committed when you are convicted of this crime. It cannot be imagined to have been committed when the defense proves your testimony untrustworthy. A testimony can be proved untrustworthy in a number of ways, including previous inconsistent statement, making improvements in testimony and incompatibility between ocular account and medical report etc. Therefore, proving a testimony untrustworthy is not the same as committing perjury. Believing the second part of a witness' statement implicating the other accused about which strong circumstantial support is available cannot be thought of as encouraging perjury. In admitting such testimony, judges are not permitting what is forbidden by law. Rather, they are separating truth from the falsehood by applying their minds to the facts of the case as opposed to mechanically disbelieving crucial testimony under the so called falsus rule.

The judgment in Ghulam Muhammad is not aimed at renouncing the falsus rule in every way. Alternatively, it provides a rule of caution reiterating the fact that all exaggerations or concealments in witness testimonies are not willful. Prosecution can prove an under-oath statement wrong, for example, by establishing that the witness was elsewhere on government duty at the time of occurrence and the witness may not have the legal cover to defend his situation. However, in reality there can be instances where a witness may not remember to apply for a leave in emergency, or he may have considered it unnecessary keeping in mind his intention to return before his physical presence is actually required. This does not make a witness untrustworthy or a liar.

The Khizer Hayat judgment provides that the function of the courts is to see whether in the light of available evidence, the charge against the accused stands proved, not to dig out the truth. As regards adversarial proceedings, the former is true and in relation to inquisitorial proceedings the latter. However, even the adversarial proceedings require the judge to assign weight- to the evidence depending upon its circumstantial corroboration, in comparison to its downright rejection for one inaccuracy.

4. Multiple interpretations of the doctrine

4.1 Referral to most rigid interpretation of the doctrine

It has been argued that the states which do not codify the rule have given three different interpretations to the maxim. According to the first, a court should absolutely disbelieve anything said by a witness who is caught in a lie. The second interpretation is permissive which stipulates that a court may or may not believe the remaining testimony. As per the third interpretation, a court must reject the remaining testimony unless corroborated in material particulars.

The first interpretation advocating that the testimony should be completely rejected if a part of it is found to be false call-in question modern psychology, according to which human beings tend to exaggerate or economize with truth in keeping with a number factors such as self-interest. It is, therefore, not certain that a person who lies about one aspect of an occurrence will be lying about the entire occurrence. Thus, for example, if a person lies about over-speeding in a traffic accident case may be telling truth about weather or brightness on the fateful day. Wigmore argues that the first interpretation concerns with weight rather than admissibility of evidence. Accordingly, judges should have the discretion to believe or disbelieve the remaining testimony of a witness who is caught in a lie about one aspect of the case. More importantly, some scholars opine that for the application of the falsus rule, it must be proved that the witness resorted to deliberate falsehood. In other words, falsehood must relate to the facts concerning which the witness could not have been liable to mistake. He resorts to the falsehood, for example in relation to the questions such as what is your country of birth, where do you live etc. Nobody in his right mind can be expected to make a mistake about these issues. In agreement with Fisher, it can be suggested that the maxim only raises a presumption. Just as the best evidence rule gives rise to the presumption that the person who withholds best evidence does this with the belief that its production will go against his self-interest, the falsus rule raises the presumption that if a witness is caught in a lie, his remaining testimony should be taken cautiously with a pinch of salt. However, as withholding of best evidence can be explained by proving that the same was given up being unnecessary, supplying incorrect information can be clarified as having been caused by mistaken identity, in- attentiveness or fading memory, not to mention material self-interest.

Unfortunately, the Khizer Hayat judgment leaves no option for the judges but to resort to the most rigid interpretation of the maxim that the remaining evidence of witness caught in lie, must in all probability be disbelieved.

4.2. Misplaced reliance on a scholarly article: Jury's role as a lie detector

Jury's role as a lie detector is an out of place scholarly article in Khizer Hayat judgment. What this article says is that in ancient times juries were not trusted for their ability to determine the credibility of a witness; hence different rules were evolved to guide them. One of these rules was that sworn witnesses would not lie, another rule was if one witness reported affirmative of an occurrence and the other witness testified negative of the same, the former should be believed. Giving priority to the testimony of affirmative later came to be known as Bethel's rule. Likewise; rules were developed to require corroboration for accomplice's testimony and testimony of the rape victim. These rules were meant to establish the sanctity of sworn testimony and hinted suspicion on jury's ability to distinguish truth from falsehood. However, after 20th century this distrust in jury's ability to separate truth from falsehood started to fade away. Accordingly, rules on corroboration of rape victim's testimony and accomplice's testimony were repealed. Along with them went rules like falsus in uno, falsus in omnibus. Therefore, all limits on jury's role as lie detectors were removed. The Supreme Court's argument in Khizer Hayat is contrary to what has been relied upon by it to put it forward. What the article Jury's role as a lie detector suggests is that now the modern trend is towards giving more freedom to jury to determine credibility of a witness. Hence, new rules are being developed such as giving consideration to out of the court statements of a child rape victim. In this way, even hearsay rule is being relaxed to allow jury to determine the truth. Conversely, Khizer Hayat circumscribes the role of the court to determining guilt or innocence in the light of available evidence.

4.3 Indian case law in Juxtaposition with Khizer Hayat

According to the jurisprudence of Indian courts starting from Balkha Singh case, there is no such rule as false in one thing, false in everything. In Balkha Singh, the Indian Supreme Court observed that it is the responsibility of courts to separate truth from falsehood in a witness testimony, in the same way as grain is separated from chaff. This can only be done if the falsehood is separable from the truth, where both are inseparable, the court will have to look for corroboration. If one or two witnesses or circumstances corroborate the statement of a witness, innocent lapses can be disregarded. In *Ahir v. State of Bihar*, the Supreme court held that there is no evidence or witness statement in which truth is not mixed up with falsehood, or which does not contain embellishments. It is the responsibility of the court to separate truth from falsehood. Indian courts further clarified that the maxim is not a rule of evidence but is a rule of caution. It is concerned with weight of the evidence and not its admissibility. That there is a clear-cut difference between discarded (inadmissible) and disregarded testimony (appraisal). In *Mithu v. Bihar*, the court held that a witness who is pressurized by an unlawful assembly, his statement should be carefully evaluated. It should be only deemed credible if corroborated by other witness statement or circumstantial evidence. Even a single statement can suffice to justify a conviction, provided the statement is corroborated, to prove a case what matters is the quality and not quantity of evidence. The court has the responsibility to carefully understand and consider the credibility of the statement. In view of the above, it can be argued that the maxim is inapplicable for determining whether a statement is to be accepted or rejected, the sole standard is corroboration. In the presence of corroboration, the innocent lapses shall be ignored but where there is an apparent desire to conceal the truth, the statement/ testimony shall automatically be rejected.

4.4 Reference to the OJ Simpson

The Supreme Court in Khizer Hayat specifically referred to an article as protagonist and upholder of the falsus rule. In this article, the author alluded to Judge Ito's instruction to the jury in OJ Simpson not to believe a witness who lied in some part of his testimony. In the opinion of the Supreme Court in Khizer Hayat, it was a modern version of the falsus rule which suggested that if a witness lied about one material fact in a part of his statement; his remaining testimony could be disbelieved. On a closer look, use of falsus in OJ Simpson was discussed in the article to recount the history of a dying rule. I suppose, the Supreme Court's passing mention to the OJ Simpson caused weakening of its own argument about revival of falsus. If the application of the rule can result in offenders like OJ escaping punishment, such a rule should better left buried in the dustbin of history. Anyone following the OJ Simpson should know that the jury's verdict in this case was widely criticized as a dark chapter in the history of US jurisprudence. For example, Britannica calls it as one of the most notorious criminal trial in American history. It was believed that the jurors were influenced by the racist angle given to the case. Moreover, one critical mistake by the prosecutors induced a not guilty verdict as the prosecution failed to prove the guilt beyond reasonable doubt. The team of extraordinary lawyers engaged by OJ outwitted the prosecution through casting a doubt on the authenticity of circumstantial evidence. It is still thought to be a controversial decision and is not celebrated as a landmark trial. In fact, OJ was found liable for wrongful death in the civil suit connected with the matter and had to pay \$ 33.5 million in damages to the heirs of the victims. Therefore, it can be argued that comment on OJ Simpson in Khizer Hayat was not only out of place but also uncalled for.

5. The impact of Khizer Hayat on jurisprudence of Pakistan

5.1 2020 MLD 1218 (Sindh)

The impact of the judgment can be seen by analyzing the judgments of the superior courts before and after Khizer Hayat. For example, in a double murder case tried before an ATC court the accused were found guilty beyond reasonable doubt. There were some absconders in the case, during the appeal against conviction of the accused; the absconders were also arrested on the pointation of complainant and eye witnesses. Their trial separately began in the ATC Sukkur. In this trial, the complainant and PWs stated in their testimony that they were not the same accused. The ATC court set them free. In appeal filed by the convicted accused, the appellate court invoked the falsus rule as laid down by the SC in Khizer Hayat and held that if the complainant and witnesses were found to be lying against some of the accused, or a material part of the case, their testimony cannot be relied against other accused or other aspects of the case. So, the convicted accused was also set free, because falsus was now law of the land. However, the facts of this case indicate that the witnesses may have lied because of social pressure, fear for their lives or monetary compensation.

5.2 2021 MLD 1097

Similarly, in 2021 MLD 1097 (Peshawar), the complainant was disbelieved for improvements made in his court testimony as compared to the FIR's story. The complainant was found to be unworthy of credit because he did not mention the time of occurrence before the court whereas he did mention the same before police. Furthermore, his testimony was in conflict with other PWs who testified that dead body of deceased was carried in cot whereas the complainant stated that it was carried in the car to DHQ. Finally, rather surprisingly, it was observed by the High Court that it looked unbelievable that the attackers spared the complainant while they took the life of his brother. It seems like the court had made up its mind that the complainant was untrustworthy and thereafter merely looked for reasons to prove its hypothesis, so that the falsus rule could be invoked. If the courts will record their judgments keeping a conclusion in mind, they will only be looking for justifications for something they have pre-decided. So, apparently, the falsus rule is encouraging the courts to shrug off their responsibility to separate truth from falsehood which could very likely be intertwined in the same statement. This is because the Khizer Hayat judgment vehemently criticized the legal position that on the one hand, witnesses are allowed to mix truth with falsehood and on the other, we are being asked to sift grain from chaff, the dislike for this duty is therefore perceivable in the judgments subsequent to Khizer Hayat.

5.3 2002 SCMR 1842

In contrast to the above, the judgments prior to Khizer Hayat brushed aside minor discrepancies and relied on circumstantial support to dig out the truth. For example, in *Elahi Bakhsh v. Rab Nawaz* (2002 SCMR 1842) it was observed "In the state of sensation and panic it is not justified to expect from a witness that he would mention the instance with exactitude as nobody bothers for any measurement in such a situation. Discrepancies in evidence of prosecution were not worth consideration..." where death occurs due to fire arm injury, it hardly matters as to whether 12 bore gun was used or a 7 MM rifle shot culminated into death of deceased.

Conclusion

The restoration of a discarded and redundant rule can be interpreted as an attempt by the court to escape from the onerous responsibility to separate truth from falsehood. Khizer Hayat has inflicted a blow to the jurisprudence of Pakistan which is pushed several decades back to adopt a controversial doctrine which at best can be called a rule of caution to determine weight of evidence, rather than its admissibility. There can hardly be

a testimony where falsehood is not mixed up with truth or exaggerations or embellishments are not made. It is the task of judge to discard falsehood at the time of appreciation of evidence by seeing which statement finds circumstantial support. A witness may give an incorrect statement because of many factors, such as a mistake, in- attentiveness, memory lapse or self-interest, owing to which his statement should be closely scrutinized. Still, this should affect the weight or probative force of evidence at the time of appraisal; it must not in any case impact the admissibility of evidence. In Latigo case, it was held that falsus rule merely raises a presumption that if a witness lies in one part, his remaining testimony shall be carefully scrutinized. It is the responsibility of the court to find out the truth hidden in the testimony of a witness. If the statement does not inspire confidence, it shall be disregarded in appraisal of evidence. Considering the foregoing, it is recommended that the rule be given a realistic interpretation keeping in view standard international practices. For instance, the version introduced by Justice Munir in Ghulam Muhammad provides a middle ground that a witness who lies in one part of his statement, his entire testimony should be discarded unless corroborated by circumstantial evidence. This version merits to be restored because it neither disregards the falsehood nor envisions the crumbling of an entire case for one incorrect or false statement.

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